

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF DESORPTION CO₂ IN CATALYTIC METHYLDIETHANOLAMINE (MDEA) SOLUTION USING THE PACKED COLUMN

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Abstract

The process of separating carbon dioxide (CO₂) is a very important thing to do in industrial processes. In industry, especially petrochemical industry, oil and natural gas in the process is needed separation of CO₂ gas where this gas is a gas of corrosive (acid gas). In the process, absorption cannot stand alone, there should be a process of regeneration of solvents or commonly called desorption. Desorption is a solute separation operation from the liquid phase to the gas phase. So the soluble CO₂ gas as a result of the absorption process can be separated from the solvent to obtain a pure CO₂ gas [1]. It is important to do the CO₂ desorption process, one of which is the desorption of CO₂ from the CO₂ absorption solution in the MDEA solution MSG and Arginine promoters. This study was conducted to determine the effect of reboiler temperature and feed flow rate on the desorption efficiency. In addition, a comparison of desorption efficiency values for each type of feed will be conducted. The method used is absorption using a vessel containing the solvent contacted with CO₂ and followed by desorption on the packed column. The results is obtained from this study indicate that the higher the reboiler temperature the greater desorption efficiency for all types of feed (blank, MSG, and Arginin) i.e for MSG catalyst with a feed flow rate of 40 ml/minute and the reboiler temperature 100, 105, 110, 115, 120 (°C) obtained desorption efficiency 70.44%; 75.65%; 79.79%; 85.28% and 89.38%, respectively. The results also showed that the greater feed flow rate is obtained desorption efficiency decreased further, for MSG catalyst at the same condition, the reboiler temperature 100 °C with the feed flow rate 40 60,80 (ml/min) is obtained desorption efficiency value 70.44%, 82.94%, 88.05%.

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1. Introduction

Most industrial-scale chemical processes require the process of separating a mixture into a final product. In the processing of natural gas and petrochemical industry, it is necessary to separate corrosive CO₂ (acid gas) because it can damage the piping system. In the fertilizer industry, CO₂ gas is a by-product of the process of making ammonia, a poisonous CO₂ gas that can close the active site of the catalyst. This can inhibit the performance of the catalyst in the ammonia synthesis process, so it must be separated before going to the ammonia formation unit [2].

On the other hand, CO₂ gas is useful in the welding process, removes harmful propellant in plastics, as a carrier gas in gas chromatography analysis, ion exchange regeneration, accelerates

the increase in recovery of oil and natural gas, production of organic compounds in pharmaceuticals, freezing food, protecting food during packaging, the production of soft drinks, neutralizes alkali in the treatment of liquid waste [3]. Methods for capturing carbon dioxide are adsorption, absorption, membrane separation [4] and cryogenic [5]. Absorption method is the most commonly used method in industry. The absorption process requires a solvent (desorption) regeneration process. CO₂ gas that dissolves in the solvent due to absorption can be separated from the solvent to obtain pure CO₂ gas [1].

Many researchers has examined absorption-desorption of CO₂ gas using amine solvents and various catalysts [6] – [10]. But until now there has been no research on CO₂ gas desorption in MDEA/MSG and MDEA/Arginine solvents. In this study CO₂ desorption will be carried out using a backing column from a mixture of methyldiethanolamine (MDEA)-CO₂ as a result of absorption using arginine and MSG catalysts.

2. Method

In this study carried out reactive CO₂ gas desorption in a solution of methyldiethanolamine (MDEA) catalyst using a backing column contactor with a bait scale of 10 L. 2 inch column diameter, column height filled with ranching ring type packing with a diameter of ¼" and ½", equipped with a hot exchanger. The research implementation phase includes tool preparation, data collection, and analysis of results. The method used is a sampling method, calculating CO₂ concentration with Chittick titration analysis method [11]. The flow rate used ranges from 40 to 80 ml per minute. The desorption operating temperature is set at a temperature range of 100°C-120°C [10]. Equipment series can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. A series of desorption devices

3. Result and Discussion

This study aims to determine the effect of reboiler temperature and feed flow rate on desorption efficiency. Desorption efficiency is defined as the ability to release CO₂ dissolved in a solvent. The measured response is desorption efficiency. The solvent used is a solution of methyldiethanolamine (MDEA). Each of these solutions is added with the amino acid salt methylsodium glutamate (MSG) and arginine amino acids. The desorption process is carried out by varying the type of catalyst, reboiler temperature, and feed flow rate. This reboiler temperature variation is (100, 105, 110, 115, 120) °C and the variation of feed flow rate is (40, 60, 80) ml/minute.

3.1. Effect of Reboiler Temperature on Desorption Efficiency

From the experimental data obtained a graph of the relationship between the temperatures of the reboiler and desorption efficiency as follows:

Figure 2. Effect of Reboiler Temperature on Desorption Efficiency at Flow Rate 40 ml/min.

Figure 3. Effect of Reboiler Temperature on Desorption Efficiency at Flow Rate 60 ml/min.

Figure 4. Effect of Reboiler Temperature on Desorption Efficiency at Flow Rate 80 ml/min.

In Figures 2, 3 and 4 shows the higher the reboiler temperature, is directly proportional to the desorption efficiency for each type of solvent and a certain flow rate. As the temperature increases, the reaction rate increases. This is due to an increase in the amount of CO₂ gas in the reaction of the solvent. This correlates with the equation of the reaction rate constants of the MDEA reaction with CO₂ gas as a function of temperature [12], as follows:

$$k_{MDEA} = 5.86 \times 10^6 \exp(-3984 / T) \quad (1)$$

The reactions that occur in the desorption process are as follows [13]:

The desorption reaction is a very endothermic reaction [14]. If the temperature gets higher then more CO₂ is released. And increasing the temperature of the gas affects the diffusivity of the gas [15]. This increase in diffusivity value, the easier the rate of mass transfer from the liquid phase to the gas. This can increase the percentage of desorption.

3.2. Effect of Feed Flow Rate on Desorption Efficiency for Each Catalyst

From the experimental data, it is made a graph of the relationship between the feed flowrate and desorption efficiency for each type of catalyst as follows:

Figure 5. Effect of Feed Flow Rate on Desorption Efficiency for Each Catalyst.

In Figure 5 it can be seen the relationship between the temperature of reboiler and desorption efficiency at various feed flow rates. The results showed that at certain reboiler temperatures and certain types of catalysts with various feed flow rates. From the curve shows the greater of feed flow rate, the smaller percentage of desorption efficiency. This occur because the contact surface area between the two phases gets smaller when the feed flow rate is greater.

Desorption is a mass and heat transfer event that involves contact between the gas phase and the liquid phase. At a certain temperature the liquid phase is carried out by the gas phase and a large contact surface area is needed so that mass transfer occurs [16].

3.3. Effect of Catalyst Types on Desorption Efficiency

In Figure 5 shows the effect of the type of catalyst in the same solvent and feed temperature on the desorption efficiency at the same flow rate. From the graph, it can be seen that the desorption efficiency of feed without catalyst is lower than the desorption efficiency of MSG and Arginine catalysts in each operating condition. The difference in value of desorption efficiency of blank or without catalyst feed occurs because the catalyst affects the reactive desorption process, the presence of a catalyst in the form of amino acids and amino acid salts that have an amine group. According to Zhang [14], the addition of amino acids and amino acid salts to amine solution (alkanolamine) can reduce the activation energy by catalyst to form intermediate reaction mechanisms with zwitterion formation. In this intermediate reaction, proton alkanolamine (MDEAH⁺) is formed which is easier to donate protons to amines (MSG and Arginine) than to donate protons to H₂O.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of studies of desorption of CO₂ gas in a catalyst MDEA solution, can be concluded as follows:

- 1) The higher the reboiler temperature, the higher the desorption efficiency obtained.
- 2) The higher the feed flow rate, the lower the desorption efficiency obtained.
- 3) In each type of feed catalyst, desorption efficiency is best obtained in MSG-catalyzed feeds, followed by Arginine catalysts and the lowest catalyst-free feed (blank).

5. References

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